

Charge-transfer and the hydrogen bond: Spectroscopic and structural implications from electronic structure calculations.

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Abstract

The absolutely localized molecular orbital (ALMO) model is a fully variational approach which permits polarization of molecules interacting in a cluster while prohibiting charge transfer (or dative interactions) between individual molecules. The ALMO model can be applied within any density functional theory calculation – the B3LYP functional is employed in this work. ALMO DFT calculations of observables such as optimized geometry, vibrational frequencies and their intensities, and vertical detachment energies are performed for the water dimer, the chloride-water complex and the cyanide water complex. The vibrational spectra are obtained both within the harmonic approximation and by quasiclassical trajectory simulations. By comparing these ALMO DFT calculations with full DFT calculations using precisely the same functional and basis, the role of charge transfer on observables in these model hydrogen bonding systems can be assessed. The results can be further interpreted using ALMO-based energy decomposition analysis, which help to reveal the origin of sensitivity or insensitivity of observables to dative interactions. Analysis of the results also suggests that the B3LYP functional, while qualitatively adequate, appears to somewhat overestimate charge transfer effects.

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1. Introduction

The physical and chemical contributions responsible for intermolecular interactions are well-understood individually [1,2,3]. Long-range permanent electrostatic interactions couple the charges, dipole moments and quadrupole moments of interacting species. Medium-range dispersion forces provide a weak attractive potential. The local electric field due to neighboring molecules induces changes in the permanent moments that enhance attractive interactions. All the above interactions apply even when the charge distributions of the partners do not overlap. Repulsive interactions arise from the overlap of the electron density of two separate molecules. In orbital terms, this is due to interacting pairs of filled orbitals (so-called Pauli repulsions), which deform the electron density. Additionally, attractive donor-acceptor interactions can arise between overlapping pairs of orbitals where one is filled and the other is empty, leading to partial charge transfer between the interacting molecules. The richness and complexity of the electronic structure of intermolecular interactions arises from the interplay of all of the above effects together. Collectively they lead to the object of interest in this paper – the hydrogen bond [4,5,6].

Molecular clusters provide an ideal vehicle for both experimental and simulation studies of hydrogen bonding [7,8,9,10]. At the level of molecular dimers, for instance, only one or two hydrogen bonds may be evident. The spectroscopic signature of the intermolecular interaction, perhaps in a vibrational spectrum, or a photoelectron spectrum, etc, will accordingly be easiest to attribute to the effect of a specific hydrogen bond interaction. In the context of this paper, the water dimer, the chloride-water dimer, and the cyanide water dimer will be re-examined using some relatively unconventional simulation methods. The rich existing literature on these hydrogen-bonded systems will be reviewed in detail later on. Our goal in this work is to try to shed some light on the comparative roles of intermolecular polarization and intermolecular charge transfer in these hydrogen bonds, and their spectroscopic signatures, using electronic structure calculations that separate these effects.

Figure 1. The minimum energy geometry of the water dimer is shown in panel (a), and does not exhibit optimal alignment of molecular dipole moments, preferring instead a near-parallel alignment of the hydrogen bond with the OH bond of the proton donor (H_D). A higher energy transition structure, shown in panel (b), does have optimal alignment of the molecular dipoles. These geometries were optimized at the B3LYP/aug-cc-pVTZ level of theory.

As a generalization it may be stated at the outset that the behavior of key experimental observables upon hydrogen bond formation is well-established, but the physical origins of these behaviors are more ambiguous. For instance, the water dimer has an equilibrium geometry of the

form shown in panel (a) of Figure 1. The hydrogen bond is nearly linear, with an alignment of the molecular dipoles that is clearly not optimal. But does this reflect local electrostatics, or orbital interactions, or a delicate interplay of both? An alternative cyclic geometry, shown in the second panel, is a saddle point on the potential energy surface, despite its more favorable alignment of dipole moments. At the global minimum, the vibrational frequency associated with the proton donor OH bond of the water dimer undergoes a characteristic red shift of about 70 cm^{-1} , and a substantial increase in intensity. To what extent are these effects a direct result of charge transfer between the two species versus polarization within the molecule?

The outline of the remainder of the paper is as follows. In Section 2, we describe the non-standard aspects of the calculations reported here. The first one concerns modifications to density functional theory calculations that we employ to separate intramolecular polarization from intermolecular charge transfer. While there are many ways to make such a separation, the one we employ here has the virtue of treating polarization variationally, via the absolutely localized orbital model. The second non-standard aspect is the quasi-classical trajectory approach that we use to simulate the vibrational spectrum with inclusion of anharmonicity – this is potentially important for clusters which typically are fluxional. In Section 3, we report results for the 3 hydrogen-bonded dimers – the water dimer, the cyanide-water dimer and the chloride-water dimer. The primary focus is the effect of hydrogen-bonding on the vibrational spectrum, and how those effects may be partitioned between polarization and charge transfer. A secondary focus is the way in which the vertical detachment energies responsible for photoelectron spectra shift depend on the polarization and charge transfer contributions to the intermolecular interactions. This question is investigated for the cyanide-water dimer, whose photoelectron spectrum has recently been the subject of both experimental and theoretical study [11,12]. The final section is a discussion of what has been learned from the calculations, as well as their possible limitations, and the implications of our findings for the spectroscopy of other molecular clusters and tools such as Stark tuning spectroscopy.

2. Computational methods.

All electronic structure calculations reported in this paper are performed using density functional theory (DFT) [13,14]. We primarily employ the very widely used B3LYP functional [15,16,17], with large enough atomic orbital (AO) basis sets to be reasonably close to the basis set limit for molecular cluster calculations. There are better functionals for intermolecular interactions (e.g. [18,19,20,21]), but the performance of B3LYP is generally satisfactory for individual hydrogen bonds [22]. We employ the aug-cc-pVTZ basis [23,24] for calculations of properties at the equilibrium geometry (optimized geometry, vibrational frequencies, infrared intensities, and energy decompositions). For more computationally intensive trajectory calculations of spectra (described below), we use the much smaller 6-31+G** set [25,26], which is perhaps the smallest reasonable choice. All electronic structure calculations were performed with a development version of the Q-Chem 4.0 package [27].

The first non-standard aspect of the calculations is the separation of intramolecular polarization from intermolecular charge transfer, mentioned briefly in the introduction. To treat polarization without charge transfer, we employ the Absolutely Localized MO (ALMO) approximation [28]. The ALMO approximation forces the AO to MO transformation matrix, \mathbf{C} , to be block-diagonal in the molecules or ions that compose the cluster. Thus for a dimer composed of interacting monomers A and B as studied herein, the occupied MO coefficient matrix is approximated as:

$$\mathbf{C}_{ALMO} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{C}_{AA} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{C}_{BB} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

By imposing the condition that the molecular orbitals on fragment A have contributions only from the atomic orbitals on fragment A, the physical effect of charge transfer between the fragments is prohibited, as is the unphysical artifact of basis set superposition error. Subject to the approximation given in Eq. (1), the DFT energy is then variationally minimized. Note that the AO basis density matrix is constructed from Eq. (1) as $\mathbf{P}_{ALMO} = \mathbf{C}_{ALMO} \mathbf{g}^{-1} \mathbf{C}_{ALMO}^\dagger$ where \mathbf{g} is the matrix of the occupied ALMO orbitals with each other. This overlap matrix is not forced to be diagonal, and thus ALMO's on one fragment overlap those on another. The ALMO approximation has been explored under various different names over the past several decades [29,30,31,32,33], and we have developed an efficient implementation [28] that is substantially faster than a conventional DFT calculation. Geometry optimizations and vibrational frequency calculations will be performed with the ALMO approximation and compared against unconstrained DFT calculations to assess the effect of charge transfer on properties of the complex.

As a variational method with a simple and physically transparent Hilbert space constraint, the ALMO approximation can be directly applied within DFT. The principal limitation to bear in mind about the ALMO approximation that it depends on the basis functions being well-localized to the fragments to which they belong. Accordingly, the ALMO approximation is ill-defined when the AO basis set is linearly dependent in the sense that functions on one fragment can represent those on another. Fortunately, tests of the ALMO approximation on the water dimer in aug-cc-pVXZ series of basis sets [34] show that the approximation yields results that are quite stable with respect to improvements in the basis set all the way up to aug-cc-pV5Z. This is undoubtedly close enough to the complete basis set limit in DFT calculations for the ALMO approach to be quite useful in practice for hydrogen-bonded systems.

The ALMO calculation can also be employed as an ingredient in an energy decomposition analysis (EDA) [35,36] of a full DFT calculation. By doing so, one gains potential additional insight relative to other widely used EDA's that do not variationally separate intra-molecular polarization from inter-molecular charge transfer (the Kitaura-Morokuma method [37] and improved variants [38,39,40,41,42] belong to this category). The binding energy between two monomers can be expressed as follows:

$$\Delta E = \Delta E_{GD} + \Delta E_F + \Delta E_P + \Delta E_{CT} \quad (2)$$

Here the individual terms are:

- “Geometric Distortion” (GD): the energy to distort a free molecule to its cluster geometry. This is evaluated as the energy difference between conventional calculations at the two geometries of each constituent of the cluster.
- “Frozen orbital” (F) interaction: the combination of permanent electrostatics and the Pauli repulsion between filled orbitals, which are taken from calculations on the isolated molecules (at their cluster geometry). Electrostatics and Pauli repulsion are not separable because electrostatics alone corresponds to an interaction with densities that are generally non-n-representable. The frozen orbital interaction is evaluated as the energy associated with the initial guess ALMO density matrix: $\mathbf{P}_{ALMO}^{(0)} = \mathbf{C}_{ALMO}^{(0)} (\mathbf{g}^{(0)})^{-1} (\mathbf{C}_{ALMO}^{(0)})^\dagger$, using the MO coefficients from calculations on the fragments without interaction.
- “Polarization” (P) effects: the energy lowering due to density relaxation without charge transfer. Computationally, the polarized energy is obtained variationally by the self-consistent ALMO calculation [28], discussed in Eq. (1) above. Thus the energy lowering associated with polarization relative to the frozen orbital interaction is exactly that obtained during the ALMO iterations. Use of the ALMO's to variationally treat polarization is a key advantage relative to other EDA's, and was first employed by Mo et al [43].
- “Charge Transfer” (CT) effects: the energy-lowering due to donor-acceptor orbital interactions. This can be separated into two terms, where the first is *pairwise-additive*:

$$\Delta E_{CT} = \text{Tr}[\mathbf{X}_{OV} \mathbf{F}_{VO}] + \Delta E_{HO} \quad (3)$$

\mathbf{F} is the Fock matrix obtained at the end of the ALMO calculation, and \mathbf{X} is the generator of the unitary transformation that changes the ALMO's as a result of diagonalizing \mathbf{F} [44]. In other words, the total energy lowering associated with this term is obtained by a single diagonalization after the ALMO SCF is complete. The fact that the charge-transfer correction can be divided into pairwise additive forward and back-donation terms is a second key advantage of the ALMO EDA. The pairwise term dominates the residual “higher order” term not just for weak interactions but for quite strong interactions as well. The residual term contains “higher order” (HO) charge transfer effects which are not pairwise decomposable and reflect additional polarization that occurs in response to charge transfer. The HO term is obtained by subtracting the final SCF energy from the energy including just the pair-wise additive contributions.

We are concerned with the comparative role of intramolecular polarization versus intermolecular charge transfer on key observables associated with hydrogen bonding in clusters. Let us briefly review a few basic concepts regarding these associations. The first observables to consider are equilibrium geometries, associated with zero forces, and positive curvature for all small displacements. Changes in H-bond distances correlate with the strength of the hydrogen bond. Second are shifts in intramolecular vibrational frequencies, particularly modes associated with the OH stretch of water, due to hydrogen bonding. The harmonic frequencies are related to the second derivative of the energy with respect to each normal coordinate,

$\omega_j = (2\pi c)^{-1} \sqrt{\partial^2 E / \partial Q_j^2}$, so shifts in these frequencies can often be interpreted as changes in the strength of the associated bond(s). Finally, the corresponding intensities of vibrational transitions can also be affected by hydrogen bonding. In the harmonic approximation, a given vibrational intensity is related to the derivative of the dipole moment with respect to the corresponding normal coordinate, $I_j \propto |\partial \mu / \partial Q_j|^2$. If displacement of a bond modulates the charge transfer associated with hydrogen bonding, we may anticipate substantial intensity changes in a cluster relative to the free molecule.

For a more realistic description of the vibrational dynamics of molecular clusters, it is desirable to go beyond the static picture due to the structural fluxionality that these systems can exhibit (cf. Ref. [45] and references therein). One approach of accounting for the fluxionality is to use trajectory sampling from molecular dynamics (MD) [46,47]. In this paper we use the quasiclassical trajectory molecular dynamics (QCT-MD) approach [48,49,50], which treats the nuclei classically, but sets up the initial velocities such that every normal mode contains zero-point vibrational energy. In recent applications to photoelectron spectra simulation [12] as well as in this paper we found that the QCT-MD trajectories have some advantages over purely classical simulations as far as the calculation of spectra is concerned. This finding is also in accordance with the literature (cf. Ref. [51] stating that "...the absence of the ZPE in the standard classical MD is a significant issue").

There are various other approaches for accurate IR spectra calculation, such as diffusion Monte Carlo (DMC) [45], the multiconfigurational time-dependent Hartree (MCTDH) approach [52], path integral Monte Carlo (PIMC) [53] and molecular dynamics (PIMD) [54], various semi-classical approximations such as ring polymer molecular dynamics (RPMD) [55], centroid molecular dynamics (CMD) [56], linearized semiclassical internal value representation (LSC-IVR) [57], and more. Some of these approaches offer a more sophisticated treatment of quantum effects, but this comes at increased cost and not without other shortcomings [58]. Since the emphasis of this paper is the investigation of charge-transfer effects on the spectra and not the underlying trajectories, we defer a detailed comparison of QCT-MD with other techniques to future work [59]. Furthermore, we refer to Ref. [12] for a detailed description of the technical details of our QCT-MD implementation.

The IR spectra in this paper are generated from the QCT-MD trajectories by using the well-known dipole autocorrelation approach [60,61]. Here, the spectral intensity is given by

$$I(\omega) \propto \omega^2 \int_0^{\infty} \langle \mu(0) \cdot \mu(t) \rangle e^{i\omega t} dt \quad (4)$$

where $\langle \mu(0) \cdot \mu(t) \rangle$ denotes the dipole autocorrelation function and the angle brackets indicate ensemble averaging. The ω^2 prefactor stems from the so-called doubly-harmonic quantum correction [62], which ensures that the (classical) correlation function satisfies the (quantum) condition of detailed balance [60,62].

3. Results.

3.1 *Water dimer.*

The water dimer is perhaps the most extensively studied molecular complex of all, both by experimental and computational methods. To briefly (and incompletely) summarize, the equilibrium geometry shown in Figure 1 is associated with a binding energy, D_e , of approximately 21 kJ/mol, by accurate ab initio calculations [63]. The ALMO method was applied to the water dimer at the Hartree-Fock level, first in pursuit of the basis set limit [64], and later with corrections for charge transfer [65]. The infrared spectrum has been intensively studied, and we shall confine ourselves here to the intramolecular motions [66,67,68,69]. Fundamentals for the bends are seen at 1601 and 1620 cm^{-1} in the gas phase, the proton donor stretch occurs at 3601 cm^{-1} , and the symmetric and asymmetric stretches of the “free” protons are at 3735 and 3746 cm^{-1} . Slight shifts are seen in matrices [70,71], where the splittings between the two localized stretch modes of the proton donor water are obtained as about 70 cm^{-1} . Additionally, considerable effort has been put into simulations of the vibrational spectrum using methods going well beyond the harmonic approximation [72,73,74].

With respect to the physical origin of the hydrogen bond, there has been, and continues to be, considerable controversy. Early Hartree-Fock calculations using the Kitaura-Morokuma approach and its variants suggested that the hydrogen bond was primarily electrostatic in origin, though the bond energy could not be adequately reproduced [37]. By contrast, the B3LYP density functional adequately describes the geometry and energetics of the water dimer, which is apparently accompanied by increased charge transfer [75]. Natural energy decomposition analysis of B3LYP calculations suggested that the hydrogen bond is primarily dative [76] (donor-acceptor interaction between O lone pair orbital and the OH σ^* orbital), as this interaction was twice the H-bond energy [77]. However this EDA does not treat electrostatics variationally and therefore exaggerates charge transfer contributions. At the other extreme, another recent calculation using constrained DFT (again with B3LYP) suggests that the contribution of permanent electrostatics is dominant [78]. Application of the variational Hilbert space ALMO EDA with the same B3LYP density functional yields a picture much closer to the earlier KM results [34], as we will review below.

While this diversity of results with different approaches is troubling, the ALMO EDA has the key merit of being fully variational for polarized interactions, frozen interaction and total interactions, within a given density functional. In addition, validation of the ALMO EDA approach to separating frozen orbital interactions, polarization interactions, and charge transfer comes from application to larger water clusters where it has been shown, as is necessary on physical grounds, that the polarization term contains by far the dominant 3-body contributions, while the frozen orbital interactions and charge transfer are primarily 2-body in character [79,80]. Further validation will emerge from the present study.

The goal of our present calculations is to assess, using the ALMO EDA, the relative importance of charge transfer between the water monomers for a variety of observables in addition to the binding energy. For this purpose, we have performed calculations on the water dimer at its equilibrium geometry (as shown in Figure 1) that are summarized in the data contained in the 2nd and 3rd columns of Table 1. Additionally we have performed the corresponding calculations at the transition structure shown in Figure 1, as given in the last two columns of the same table. Each set of calculations were performed with and without the ALMO

approximation to enable an assessment of the comparative effect of charge transfer on the structure, and vibrational frequencies and intensities at these two stationary points.

From the energetic point of view, it can be immediately seen that frozen orbital interactions, intramolecular polarization, and charge transfer are all roughly of equal importance at the minimum geometry (see column 2). There is hence a pronounced difference in the overall binding energy with and without the ALMO approximation, and the hydrogen bond is too long by about 0.2 Å when charge transfer is neglected. However, the geometric structure does not qualitatively change, despite the fact that the dipole moments of the two monomers are not optimally aligned. This reinforces the conclusion given earlier that charge transfer, while important quantitatively, is not decisive in determining the equilibrium geometry.

Table 1. Binding energy decompositions, geometry, and harmonic vibrational frequencies (cm^{-1}) and infrared intensities (km mol^{-1}) for the global minimum (min) of the water dimer and the transition structure (TS) shown in panels (a) and (b) of Figure 1, computed at the B3LYP/aug-cc-pVTZ level of theory with and without the ALMO approximation.

	ALMO (min)	Full (min)	ALMO (TS)	Full (TS)
$\Delta E / \text{kJ mol}^{-1}$	-13.7	-18.8	-9.3	-10.3
$\Delta E_{\text{fz}} / \text{kJ mol}^{-1}$	-10.5	-6.4	-8.5	-7.9
$\Delta E_{\text{pol}} / \text{kJ mol}^{-1}$	-3.2	-5.8	-1.1	-1.5
$\Delta E_{\text{CT}} / \text{kJ mol}^{-1}$	0.0	-6.8	0.0	-1.4
μ / Debye	2.7	2.9	4.0	4.4
$R(\text{O}\cdots\text{H}) / \text{Å}$	2.15	1.96	2.66	2.57
$R(\text{O}\cdots\text{O}) / \text{Å}$	3.11	2.92	3.15	3.05
$R(\text{OH}_D) / \text{Å}$	0.96	0.97	0.96	0.96
$\omega_1 (I_1)$	137 (0)	164 (1)	191i (65)	237i (59)
$\omega_2 (I_2)$	174 (69)	192 (127)	68 (12)	70 (14)
$\omega_3 (I_3)$	209 (78)	220 (32)	101 (2)	112 (2)
$\omega_4 (I_4)$	211 (201)	244 (244)	149 (227)	158 (244)
$\omega_5 (I_5)$	318 (118)	374 (74)	206 (14)	222 (3)
$\omega_6 (I_6)$	492 (123)	615 (100)	388 (252)	420 (245)
$\omega_7 (I_7)$	1636 (85)	1632 (87)	1628 (20)	1624 (6)
$\omega_8 (I_8)$	1649 (56)	1652 (45)	1645 (177)	1644 (205)
$\omega_9 (I_9)$	3791 (85)	3683 (330)	3800 (10)	3798 (13)
$\omega_{10} (I_{10})$	3803 (7)	3800 (10)	3812 (10)	3807 (11)
$\omega_{11} (I_{11})$	3895 (121)	3877 (84)	3894 (57)	3884 (53)
$\omega_{12} (I_{12})$	3902 (79)	3899 (85)	3900 (75)	3899 (76)

The transition structure involves intermolecular interactions that are about 80% frozen orbital interactions by energy, consistent with the optimal alignment of the monomer dipole moments. The difference in the optimized structure with and without the ALMO approximation is correspondingly quite small. It should be relatively unsurprising that the other properties of the complex at this geometry track each other quite closely with and without the ALMO

approximation (which removes intermolecular charge transfer). At this point on the potential energy surface, closed shell repulsive interactions plus electrostatic contributions constitute nearly a complete description of the intermolecular interaction. That is the nature of the bifurcated hydrogen bond geometry within our theoretical model.

The equilibrium geometry corresponds to a much richer and more balanced interplay of the three energetic contributions. It is therefore far less obvious how observables such as the inter and intra-molecular harmonic vibrational frequencies and their corresponding intensities will be affected by charge transfer effects relative to frozen and polarized interactions alone. The results in Table 1 give direct insight into this issue. Let us focus on the intramolecular (high frequency) modes first. The stretches are particularly interesting. The splitting between the symmetric stretches (zero for non-interacting monomers) is only 12 cm^{-1} in the ALMO approximation, but increases nearly 10-fold to 117 cm^{-1} when the full model is considered. In other words, the red shift seen in the symmetric stretch is dominated by charge transfer. This is consistent with the strong dependence of charge transfer on the HOMO-LUMO gap. Even more interestingly, the very large intensity enhancement relative to the monomer (factor of 30 or so in these calculations) is *not* correspondingly dominated by intermolecular charge transfer. There is nearly an 8-fold enhancement in the ALMO calculations already, which must be ascribed to intramolecular polarization, in the field of the neighboring molecule. This leaves a further 4-fold enhancement due to intermolecular charge transfer. These two variables (vibrational red shift, and intensity enhancement) exhibit quite different degrees of dependence on charge transfer. By contrast, the antisymmetric stretches at about 3900 cm^{-1} are much more weakly affected by complex formation, and the intramolecular bends at roughly 1640 cm^{-1} are essentially unaffected.

To go beyond the harmonic approximation, we apply the quasiclassical trajectory approach described in the Methods section, to compute the vibrational spectrum as the Fourier transform of the dipole autocorrelation function, as shown in Eq. (4). Comparing the calculated spectra with and without the ALMO approximation shows both the frequency shifts and changes in absorption intensities associated with charge transfer. The principal differences mirror those seen within the harmonic approximation – there is a red shift of slightly less than 100 cm^{-1} in the long-wave part of the band associated with OH stretches due to charge transfer. Additionally the relative intensity of long-wave length feature relative to the shorter wavelength feature associated with OH stretches reverses with the inclusion of charge transfer. In detail both OH stretch features have shifted to the red by approximately 100 cm^{-1} relative to calculations employing the harmonic approximation in the same basis.

There is fairly good agreement between the strong OH-absorption related features of the QCT simulated spectrum, and the experimental absorptions at 3601 cm^{-1} and $3735/3746\text{ cm}^{-1}$. This supports the fact that the performance of B3LYP appears to be quite adequate for the water dimer, consistent with previous literature [22,75]. But of course B3LYP is not the exact density functional. One can also compare the harmonic frequencies given in Table 1 with higher level harmonic frequency calculations using coupled cluster CCSD(T) with large basis sets [81]. The B3LYP/aug-cc-pVTZ (and CCSD(T)/aug-cc-pVQZ) frequencies are 3683 (vs 3748) cm^{-1} for $\omega(\text{OH}_D)$ and 3877 (vs 3912) cm^{-1} for $\omega(\text{OH}_F)$. Thus B3LYP slightly overestimates the the red shifting of $\omega(\text{OH}_F)$, and the $\omega(\text{OH}_F)$ - $\omega(\text{OH}_D)$ splitting, which suggests that it is slightly exaggerating the charge-transfer effects. This agrees with a recent report suggesting that B3LYP

likewise somewhat overestimates the role of charge transfer in hydrogen bonding in the water hexamer [80].

Figure 2. Vibrational spectrum for the water dimer computed at the B3LYP/6-31+G** level by the quasiclassical trajectory method described in the Methods Section, with and without the application of the ALMO approximation, which precludes intermolecular charge transfer. The difference between the two spectra thereby reflects the effect of charge transfer.

3.2 Chloride-water anion dimer

The chloride-water anion dimer has been extensively studied, both by ab initio calculations [82,83,84], and by experimental measurements [85,86,87,88,89,90,91], including extensive characterization of the infrared spectrum. In addition, there have been a range of theoretical studies of the infrared spectrum using a variety of increasingly sophisticated methods to go beyond the harmonic approximation [92,93,94,95,96]. The equilibrium geometry of the chloride-water cluster is well-established as having C_s symmetry, with a nearly linear hydrogen bond between the chloride and one proton, as shown in panel (a) of Figure 3, which also depicts the donor-acceptor orbital pair responsible for charge transfer (and discussed further below). The symmetric structure, shown in panel (b) of Figure 3 is a first order saddle point connecting two equivalent minima. Some aspects of the experimental vibrational spectrum, particularly the region associated with the proton donor stretch, are difficult to reconcile between the reported experimental spectra [85,86,90]. The calculations we have performed at these two stationary points on the potential energy surface are summarized in Table 2.

Figure 3. Principal donor orbital (bold shading) and corresponding acceptor orbital (pale shading) for the charge transfer interaction between the chloride anion (shown in aquamarine) and the water molecule at (a) the most stable asymmetric hydrogen bonding geometry and (b) the symmetric bifurcated geometry, which is a saddle point on the full electronic potential energy surface. The calculations were performed at the B3LYP/aug-cc-pVTZ level of theory, at stationary points optimized at the same level of theory. The plots correspond to a surface value of 0.1 au.

Table 2. Binding energy decompositions, geometry, and harmonic vibrational frequencies (cm^{-1}) and infrared intensities (km mol^{-1}) for the global minimum (asym) of the chloride-water anion dimer and the symmetric structure (sym) shown in Figure 3, computed at the B3LYP/aug-cc-pVTZ level of theory with and without the ALMO approximation.

	ALMO (asym)	Full (asym)	ALMO (sym)	Full (sym)
$\Delta E / \text{kJ mol}^{-1}$	-45.8	-59.4	-44.8	-51.5
$\Delta E_{\text{fz}} / \text{kJ mol}^{-1}$	-36.0	-23.1	-38.5	-37.3
$\Delta E_{\text{pol}} / \text{kJ mol}^{-1}$	-10.9	-18.3	-8.9	-10.6
$\Delta E_{\text{CT}} / \text{kJ mol}^{-1}$	0.0	-20.7	0.0	-8.0
$R(\text{OH}_D) / \text{\AA}$	0.97	0.99	0.97	0.97
$R(\text{Cl}\cdots\text{H}) / \text{\AA}$	2.46	2.14	2.82	2.65
$\angle(\text{ClHO}) / \text{deg}$	156	169	116	115
$\omega_1 (I_1)$	150 (33)	209 (25)	143 (93)	300i (93)
$\omega_2 (I_2)$	269 (46)	391 (45)	154 (15)	140 (17)
$\omega_3 (I_3)$	627 (104)	747 (55)	616 (144)	669 (117)
$\omega_4 (I_4)$	1690 (120)	1672 (100)	1691 (219)	1654 (309)
$\omega_5 (I_5)$	3719 (251)	3286 (1173)	3798 (42)	3739 (133)
$\omega_6 (I_6)$	3863 (48)	3864 (19)	3836 (53)	3746 (30)

Let us first consider effect of the ALMO approximation on the asymmetric geometry. It is evident from the EDA that charge transfer accounts for approximately 33% of the binding energy at the equilibrium geometry, and therefore its neglect in the ALMO approximation should be expected to substantially affect calculated properties. Indeed this is the case. The asymmetric

minimum survives, but with the Cl \cdots H distance substantially elongated by about 0.3 Å, and a shift of the 13° in the ClHO angle. The reason for the dramatic change in geometry is quite straightforward. Both attractive charge-transfer and repulsive Pauli interactions damp exponentially with separation between the hydrogen-bonding partners, while the electrostatic interactions change more slowly. If we exclude the CT contribution, then elongating the Cl \cdots H distance will relax the repulsive Pauli interactions while more weakly affecting the attractive electrostatic interactions. This is the primary origin of the difference between the ALMO optimized geometry and the geometry optimization without the ALMO approximation.

In Figure 3, the principal donor-acceptor orbital pairs are plotted for the asymmetric and symmetric geometries of the chloride water anion dimer. These orbitals come directly from singular value decomposition of the matrix \mathbf{X} in Eq. (3) [36], and it is satisfying to see that their appearance is exactly as would be anticipated from frontier orbital arguments. The principal donor orbital is the chloride p orbital that is oriented appropriately to interact with the OH bonds of the water molecule. The corresponding principal acceptor orbital has anti-bonding σ^* character on the OH_D bond for the asymmetric geometry (corresponding to the minimum), and is a delocalized superposition of OH antibonding orbitals at the symmetric geometry. In the latter case the CT interaction is considerably weaker as a result of the less optimal orbital alignment. At the asymmetric geometry, the 0.02 Å lengthening of the OH_D distance due to CT is a direct consequence of the charge transfer into the σ^* orbital.

As can be seen in Table 2, application of the ALMO approximation also has a dramatic effect on the vibrational frequencies and intensities associated with the OH_D stretch, where H_D is the proton donor, while the OH_F stretch (where H_F is the free proton) is nearly unaffected. The splitting of 578 cm⁻¹ between the two OH stretching modes in the full calculation is reduced by more than a factor of 4 to only 144 cm⁻¹ when the ALMO approximation is applied. We may therefore conclude that the primary origin of the large splitting is indeed directly associated with charge transfer (at least 75%) from the chloride lone pairs to the $\sigma^*(\text{OH}_D)$ antibonding orbital. This reflects the fact that while CT is a minority contributor (33%) to the overall chloride-water interaction, it has by far the strongest effect on the OH_D force constant. Stretching the OH_D bond directly shifts the energy of the $\sigma^*(\text{OH}_D)$ orbital down or up, which increases CT, and thereby weakens the force constant relative to the free molecule. The effect of excluding CT on the vibrational intensity of ω_5 is also dramatic – with more than a 4-fold reduction in the corresponding calculation employing the ALMO approximation. The dipole derivative with respect to Q_5 (the OH_D stretch) is therefore very sensitive to charge transfer as well.

The symmetric geometry exhibits a substantially reduced contribution from CT and also from polarization, as the coupling between the permanent dipole moment of water and the charge of chloride is now more optimal. Therefore the difference between ALMO results and those obtained without the ALMO approximation for geometry, binding energy, and the OH vibrations is now greatly decreased. However, the topology of the ALMO potential energy surface has been altered – the symmetric structure is a minimum rather than a transition structure. The ALMO approximation gives a differentially better description of the symmetric geometry relative to asymmetric ones where neglect of CT is a stronger approximation. The fact that CT effects change significantly in strength with asymmetric displacement causes the symmetric geometry to be a minimum on the ALMO potential energy surface. In this case, CT is essential for obtaining a potential energy surface that is qualitatively correct.

The next results are trajectory calculations of the vibrational spectrum for the chloride water cluster, as shown in Figure 4. We focus on the high-frequency modes associated with the OH stretches, and in this case explore the difference between quasiclassical and classical trajectory calculations. There is a significant difference between the classical and quasiclassical absorptions associated with the OH_D and OH_F modes. The QCT spectrum exhibits a red shift of about 100 cm⁻¹ for the OH_F mode which brings it from roughly 3850 cm⁻¹ in the classical MD spectrum (which is very close to the harmonic value) to about 3750 cm⁻¹ in the QCT spectrum. The result is in substantially better agreement with the experimental value of 3690 cm⁻¹, showing the value of the QCT approach for a well-separated vibrational mode. This agrees with the findings of Ref. [97], in which it is stated that classical trajectories "... do not sample the anharmonic regions of the potential that are relevant to the experimental spectrum" and that a quasiclassical spectrum "... is more closely related to the experimental one".

Figure 4. Trajectory calculations of the vibrational spectrum of the chloride water cluster at room temperature, using the B3LYP/6-31+G** potential energy surface for classical trajectories and the corresponding quasi-classical trajectories (QCT).

The situation is much more complicated for the intense absorption associated with the OH_D mode. Indeed the experimental situation is also complicated, with different groups reporting results that do not appear to be compatible. Nevertheless, the most sophisticated calculations [95,96] show two intense peaks at 3123 cm⁻¹ and 3170 cm⁻¹, and the QCT spectrum appears roughly consistent with this result, though shifted to higher frequency by approximately 100 cm⁻¹. By contrast, the classical MD spectrum associated with the OH_D motion exhibits a single intense feature that is shifted at least 200 cm⁻¹ to the blue.

Finally, as we did for the water dimer, we can make some further assessment of the adequacy of the B3LYP functional itself for describing charge transfer by comparing the splitting between the B3LYP calculated harmonic frequencies for in Table 2 for $\omega(\text{OH}_F) - \omega(\text{OH}_D)$

versus higher level CCSD(T)/aug-cc-pVTZ harmonic frequency calculations from the literature [95]. The B3LYP harmonic frequency splitting is 578 cm^{-1} , while the CCSD(T) harmonic frequency splitting is 477 cm^{-1} . Since the B3LYP and CCSD(T) values for $\omega(\text{OH}_F)$ differ by only 3 cm^{-1} , while the charge-transfer sensitive $\omega(\text{OH}_D)$ mode differs by 104 cm^{-1} , this implies that B3LYP is somewhat overestimating the effect of charge transfer in the chloride-water complex.

3.3 Cyanide-water anion dimer

The cyanide-water anion dimer has two distinct minima corresponding to $\text{CN}^- \cdots \text{OH}_2$ and $\text{NC}^- \cdots \text{OH}_2$ respectively, which are shown in Figure 5, together with the orbitals primarily responsible for the dative component of hydrogen bonding. While the cyanide-water vibrational spectrum has not been obtained experimentally, it has been characterized at the harmonic level by quantum chemistry, and the potential energy surface has been explored [98,11]. Binding energy information is available from experiments [99], and quite recently the photoelectron spectrum of the complex has been reported to exhibit a quite striking shift with temperature [11,100]. This has been reasonably well reproduced by quasiclassical trajectory simulations [12], based on DFT treatment of the anion and neutral potential surfaces. In this section, we first consider the differential effect of polarization and charge transfer on the vibrational spectra and geometric properties of this cluster, much as we did for the water dimer and the chloride-water cluster in the preceding sections. We then turn to an examination of the effect of charge transfer on the vertical detachment energies of the cyanide water complex at different points on the potential energy surface.

Figure 5. Complementary donor-acceptor orbital pairs at optimized geometries of the two minima of the cyanide anion – water complex, calculated at the B3LYP/aug-cc-pVTZ level, where the N atom is olive green and the C atom is aquamarine. Panel (a) corresponds to $\text{CN}^- \cdots \text{OH}_2$ and panel (b) shows $\text{NC}^- \cdots \text{OH}_2$. The principal donor orbital (σ lone pair orbital) responsible for charge transfer is shown in bold, and the corresponding acceptor orbital (OH σ^* orbital) is shown with pale shading.

The results of geometry optimization, energy decomposition analysis, and harmonic vibrational frequency calculations on the two minima of cyanide water are given in Table 3. In broad terms, the results mirror those seen for the asymmetric geometry of the chloride water cluster, and this discussion will be accordingly brief. Charge transfer plays an important role in these near linear hydrogen bonding geometries, accounting for approximately one third of the

binding energy for both conformations. The larger value for charge transfer in $\text{NC}^{\ominus}\cdots\text{OH}_2$ relative to $\text{CN}^{\ominus}\cdots\text{OH}_2$ correlates satisfyingly with the greater polarization of the lone pair orbital responsible for electron donation, shown in Figure 5. The large splitting of nearly 700 cm^{-1} between the OH_D and OH_F stretches is reduced to only about 200 cm^{-1} when the ALMO approximation is employed. As the OH_F stretch is barely affected, this indicates that charge transfer is predominantly responsible for the red shift in the OH_D stretch. CT is similarly responsible for most of the intensity enhancement. The origin of these effects can be seen in the donor-acceptor orbital pairs shown in Figure 5, which indicate coupling to the $\text{OH } \sigma^*$ orbital.

Table 3. Binding energy decompositions, geometry, and harmonic vibrational frequencies (cm^{-1}) and infrared intensities (km mol^{-1}) for the two minima ($\text{CN}^{\ominus}\cdots\text{OH}_2$ and $\text{NC}^{\ominus}\cdots\text{OH}_2$) of the cyanide water anion dimer shown in Figure 5, computed at the B3LYP/aug-cc-pVTZ level of theory with and without the ALMO approximation.

	ALMO ($\text{CN}^{\ominus}\cdots\text{OH}_2$)	Full ($\text{CN}^{\ominus}\cdots\text{OH}_2$)	ALMO ($\text{NC}^{\ominus}\cdots\text{OH}_2$)	Full ($\text{NC}^{\ominus}\cdots\text{OH}_2$)
$\Delta E / \text{kJ mol}^{-1}$	-50.4	-65.0	-47.3	-65.0
$\Delta E_{\text{ftz}} / \text{kJ mol}^{-1}$	-35.7	-18.1	-34.8	-15.3
$\Delta E_{\text{pol}} / \text{kJ mol}^{-1}$	-15.6	-28.5	-13.5	-27.1
$\Delta E_{\text{CT}} / \text{kJ mol}^{-1}$	0.0	-21.6	0.0	-26.5
$R(\text{X}\cdots\text{H}) / \text{\AA}$	2.06	1.78	2.25	1.90
$\angle(\text{CNO}) / \text{deg}$	169	172	6.4	3.9
$\omega_1 (I_1)$	71 (6)	88 (5)	80 (3)	106 (3)
$\omega_2 (I_2)$	98 (25)	103 (25)	103 (8)	121 (8)
$\omega_3 (I_3)$	191 (31)	238 (47)	161 (22)	215 (38)
$\omega_4 (I_4)$	327 (61)	451 (59)	309 (69)	458 (58)
$\omega_5 (I_5)$	695 (108)	872 (73)	671 (99)	873 (55)
$\omega_6 (I_6)$	1698 (106)	1692 (86)	1694 (102)	1682 (76)
$\omega_7 (I_7)$	2141 (39)	2148 (54)	2150 (13)	2164 (10)
$\omega_8 (I_8)$	3657 (433)	3164 (1525)	3674 (328)	3072 (1527)
$\omega_9 (I_9)$	3870 (40)	3860 (17)	3869 (40)	3854 (13)

Turning next to the CN stretch (ω_7), we see that there is only a very small shift of 7 cm^{-1} associated with the ALMO approximation for the $\text{CN}^{\ominus}\cdots\text{OH}_2$ structure. The shift is 14 cm^{-1} for the $\text{NC}^{\ominus}\cdots\text{OH}_2$ structure. We therefore see that despite the large contribution of charge transfer to the binding energy of the complex, the CN stretch is nearly invariant to its inclusion or exclusion. This is understandable from the form of the cyanide donor orbital, which as can be seen in Figure 5, is a σ lone pair centered on either N or C according to the structure. This non-bonding orbital does not affect the CN bond, and accordingly the CN stretch is quite insensitive to the charge transfer. From the viewpoint of Stark tuning spectroscopy [101,102], where the nitrile vibration is used as a reporter on the electric fields associated with its environment, this insensitivity to charge transfer is highly desirable. Further study of nitriles in more complex environments using the ALMO EDA approach could complement existing efforts [103] to

explore the differential roles of electrostatic and dative (hydrogen-bonding) effects on the nitrile stretch.

Table 4. Calculations of vertical detachment energies (VDE's) using the B3LYP/6-311++G** level of theory, with the ALMO approximation, and without the ALMO approximation (denoted as full). The B3LYP/6-311++G** geometries are employed for these calculations.

Stationary point	VDE(ALMO) / eV	VDE(Full) / eV	Deviation / eV
0. free CN ⁻	4.04	4.04	0.00
1. min(CN ⁻ ...OH ₂)	4.76	4.77	-0.01
2. min(NC ⁻ ...OH ₂)	4.69	4.86	-0.17
3. TS(min 1↔min 2)	4.74	4.75	-0.01
4. TS(min 1↔min 1)	4.66	4.65	0.02
5. TS(min 2↔min 2)	4.78	4.74	0.05

Vertical detachment energy calculations are relevant for the simulation and interpretation of photoelectron spectra. For clusters, the simulation of such spectra poses a substantial computational challenge because one must perform ab initio calculations of the VDE's not merely at stationary points, as is routine, but, if possible, at all geometries that are sampled by the large-amplitude motions of the cluster. In this way the appropriate averaging over environments of the solute is accounted for. The challenge in performing such a simulation would be greatly reduced if the environment could be partially simplified. The results contained in Table 4 show the impact of neglecting the charge transfer contribution to the VDE, due to computing it within the ALMO approximation. If the ALMO computations of the VDE's are faithful to the full calculation, this would be a reasonably promising basis for making even stronger approximations such as treating the solute (cyanide) in an embedding electric field due to the solute molecules.

The results are quite interesting. Beginning with the free cyanide, we see that there is a shift of approximately 0.6 to 0.7 eV upon complexing with a water molecule, based on the full B3LYP calculations. In contrast to this large shift upon complex formation, there are much more subtle shifts with a range of only 0.12 eV between the stationary points of the cluster. The magnitude of the blue shift in the overall VDE is quite accurately reproduced by the ALMO calculation, indicating that charge transfer is a small contributor to the overall shift in the VDE's. However, the situation is far less satisfactory when it comes to correctly distinguishing the relative VDE's at the 5 stationary points on the cyanide water surface. The relative values of the VDE's at the two minima, for example, are incorrectly ordered when the ALMO approximation is applied. Thus we conclude that the ALMO approximation is incapable of generally distinguishing the small shifts in photoelectron spectra that occur with changes in temperature or cluster preparation leading to different relative populations of cluster isomers. Of course a given density functional like B3LYP is not perfectly accurate for these calculations either, but their fidelity to coupled cluster calculations, at least for the cyanide water system has been benchmarked as adequate to describe these same small shifts.

3.4 Comparison of vibrational frequency shifts between density functionals

We have discussed how charge transfer in the hydrogen bond is primarily responsible for red-shifting the harmonic vibrational frequency associated with the proton donor, $\omega(\text{OH}_\text{D})$, and increasing the splitting between this mode and the OH stretch associated with the free proton, $\omega(\text{OH}_\text{F})$ from the difference between the antisymmetric and symmetric stretch modes of the free water molecule. The evidence for this is the substantial reduction of this splitting when the ALMO approximation is invoked, as we discussed in detail for the water dimer and the chloride water dimer. As we observed earlier, these splittings are calculated with the B3LYP functional to be slightly larger than reference values from wave function methods, a deviation which we may then associate with a slight overestimation of charge transfer effects with this functional.

Confirmation of this interpretation can be obtained by examining results with Hartree-Fock (HF) theory, which certainly underestimates charge transfer effects (as a result of the HOMO-LUMO gaps being too large; reducing frontier orbital interactions associated with CT). The results of HF harmonic vibrational frequency calculations for each of the complexes are summarized in Table 5, and compared against both B3LYP, and two more recently developed density functionals, the M06-2X hybrid meta GGA functional [19], and the ω B97X range-separated hybrid functional [21]. Relative to more reliable coupled cluster reference values (though the values quoted in the table are generally still likely to be in error by a few tens of wave numbers, due to limitations of the basis, neglect of core-valence correlation, relativistic effects etc), the HF calculations significantly underestimate the splitting between the harmonic frequencies, $\omega(\text{OH}_\text{F}) - \omega(\text{OH}_\text{D})$. Comparing with the corresponding splitting (between antisymmetric and symmetric stretches) for free water (left-hand column), shows that only a small fraction of the increase is recovered by HF. This is the anticipated consequence of HF underestimating the orbital interactions (and charge transfer) associated with hydrogen bonding.

Table 5. Calculations of the splitting (in cm^{-1}), $\omega(\text{OH}_\text{F}) - \omega(\text{OH}_\text{D})$, between the localized proton donor vibrational frequency, $\omega(\text{OH}_\text{D})$ and the corresponding free proton stretch, $\omega(\text{OH}_\text{F})$, which is sensitive to charge transfer in the hydrogen bond. The calculated values of $\omega(\text{OH}_\text{D})$ is given in parentheses (also in cm^{-1}). All HF and DFT calculations are performed with the aug-cc-pVTZ basis set, and employ the harmonic approximation.

Method	H ₂ O	H ₂ O...HOH	Cl ⁻ ...HOH	CN ⁻ ...HOH	NC ⁻ ...HOH
HF	103 (4118)	129 (4072)	255 (3965)	408 (3780)	414 (3772)
B3LYP	102 (3799)	194 (3683)	578 (3286)	696 (3164)	782 (3072)
M06-2X	101 (3915)	164 (3828)	468 (3507)	729 (3249)	807 (3164)
ω B97X	106 (3879)	202 (3752)	474 (3493)	641 (3299)	695 (3241)
Reference	109 (3831)	164 (3748) ^a	477 (3390) ^b	571 (3296) ^c	647 (3216) ^c

^a Reference CCSD(T)/aug-cc-pVQZ values from ref. [81].

^b Reference CCSD(T)/aug-cc-pVTZ values from ref. [95].

^c Reference CCSD(T)/aug-cc-pVTZ values from unpublished calculations by S. Xantheas (private communication).

While B3LYP greatly improves on HF, it does slightly overestimate the $\omega(\text{OH}_F)$ - $\omega(\text{OH}_D)$ splittings, as well as the red-shift of $\omega(\text{OH}_D)$ from the symmetric stretch of free water. Do more recently developed functionals perform better for this problem? While there are a vast number of more recent functionals, we select two for assessment. Referring again to Table 5, it is evident that the M06-2X functional, and the ωB97X functional do indeed improve upon B3LYP quite noticeably for the calculated frequency, $\omega(\text{OH}_D)$, that is sensitive to charge transfer, as well as the splitting. M06-2X performs particularly well for the $\omega(\text{OH}_F)$ - $\omega(\text{OH}_D)$ splittings for water dimer and chloride water dimer. ωB97X performs particularly well for the value of the $\omega(\text{OH}_D)$ frequency for each of the complexes (virtually identical results are obtained for these systems with the related ωB97 and $\omega\text{B97X-D}$ functionals – though the latter is to be preferred for systems where dispersion effects are more prominent). It is encouraging that both functionals exhibit roughly similar improvements relative to B3LYP, and thus it may be preferable to employ these newer functionals in future work. Nonetheless, the qualitative performance of B3LYP is certainly adequate, and it is also true that neither of the new functionals is a strictly faithful mimic of the coupled cluster benchmarks.

4. Discussion and conclusions.

Several general points may be drawn from the results presented here, where we have employed the absolutely localized molecular orbital (ALMO) model to assess the effect of charge transfer on geometric and spectroscopic observables in the water dimer, the chloride-water dimer, and the cyanide-water dimer. All calculations were performed with the standard B3LYP functional, and therefore the following conclusions technically apply only to B3LYP. Fortunately, B3LYP observables are generally quite reliable for the systems studied here.

(1) In linear hydrogen bonding geometries for the clusters studied here, charge transfer accounts for approximately 30% of the binding energy, and has a very large effect on the vibrational frequency and intensity associated with the localized OH_D stretch, where H_D is the proton donor. The effect on other modes, such as for example the nitrile stretch, can still be very small.

(2) At other geometries where the linear hydrogen bond is broken, such as the symmetric arrangement of chloride with water, the charge transfer contribution is greatly diminished. Observables calculated with the ALMO approximation then show generally better agreement with experiment at such geometries.

(3) The variational Hilbert space separation between intramolecular polarization and intermolecular charge transfer appears to work reasonably well in these systems, and give useful insight. For instance, inspection of the principal donor-acceptor orbitals can often straightforwardly explain the sensitivity or insensitivity of a given vibration to charge transfer.

(4) The calculations and computational approach are limited by the accuracy of the density functional itself, as the present formulation of the theory is limited to self-consistent wavefunctions. Our results suggest while the B3LYP functional is qualitatively correct, it somewhat overestimates charge transfer effects. These errors can be reduced with range-separated hybrids such as ωB97X , or hybrid meta GGA's such as M06-2X. The second potential limitation is that as the atomic orbital basis approaches overcompleteness, the separation between intramolecular polarization and intermolecular charge transfer breaks down. However, there is little evidence that this is occurring, even with the quite large basis sets employed herein.

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